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Automatic delineation of river centerline using high density topographic LiDAR point cloud

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Abstract—LiDAR topographic data are more and more used in fluvial geomorphology where the delineation of the river water surface remains problematic. Indeed, the random absorption of infrared rays by water and by dense vegetation complicates the task of deterministic algorithms when working at a very large scale. These algorithms mainly use intensity and density of points to separate water from land but their threshold can vary depending on the transmitter and the study site characteristics. This work aims to delineate the centerline of rivers using a progressive research along the river path using only scatter of topographic LiDAR 3D points. We used the high point density, accuracy and classification of the newly created French IGN LiDAR HD to create a model calculating flow direction helping in river centerline delineation. The issues involved by the heterogeneity of the data are therefore limited thanks to the use of 8 different indicators instead of only the density and/or intensity factor. Results on 32 river reaches show a mean error of 23.65% and a median error of 8.5% of the river width coming from LiDAR automated river centerlines compared to references centerlines.

I. INTRODUCTION

The precise location of the centerline of a watercourse is often one of the first needs of fluvial geomorphologists, hydrologists and hydrobiologists. When it is not measured in the field [1,2] or drawn manually [3], the centerline of fluvial channels is often calculated from the polygon corresponding to the water surface, itself identified using various methods, on DTMs, satellite images or orthophotographs. Unlike the location of the top of the banks, which is assumed to be relatively stable through time, the water surface of a river is an object whose shape and size highly change over time. They are intrinsically linked to the hydrological conditions of the river at the time of acquisition and to the cross-section shape of the river. Over the past 30 years, the development of high-resolution aerial and satellite topography techniques has led to the creation of numerous semi-automatic or fully automatic methods for identifying the water surface, which are still widely used nowadays. Methods based on satellite data (imagery, GNSS reflectometry, RaDAR) are developing strongly thanks to global

Rétat, Alexandre LGP UPEC ; Thommeret, Nathalie LGP UPEC ; Gob, Frédéric LGP UP1PS ; Bailly, Jean-Stéphane LISAH Univ. Montpellier ; Lespez, Laurent LGP UPEC ; Kreutzenberger, Karl OFB ; space missions such as Landsat, SWOT or Sentinel, but are mostly limited to large rivers (~50m wide).

On a smaller scale, aerial or drone imagery and Canny filters give good results, but are rapidly limited when vegetation covers a substantial part of the water surface [4,5,6,7], which is mainly the case for narrower rivers. To limit the difficulties associated with the presence of vegetation and improve the data density and the geometric accuracy, others methods use LiDAR data to extract elevation DTMs and information such as point density and intensity, in order to distinguish ground from water [8,9,10,11,12]. In France, a high-resolution LiDAR coverage is carried out nationwide by the French Geographic National Institute (IGN). At that scale, the LiDAR data provided by IGN are inevitably not homogeneous in terms of density and intensity, making it difficult to use a deterministic method to delineate the centerline of very long river reaches. The aim of this work is to propose a direct method for determining the centerline of rivers for which the full water surface is unknown, and which can be better adapted to the characteristics of the river channel (river morphology, riparian vegetation) and the LiDAR data (density). Three issues are therefore addressed: i) consideration of data heterogeneity (density, intensity), ii) consideration of study site heterogeneity (hydromorphological characteristics), iii) computer time and resources optimization.

II. OPPORTUNITIES AND LIMITATIONS OF THE LiDAR DATA

The airborne HD LiDAR data provided by the IGN is characterized by a very high density of points (10 pulses per m², i.e. around 30M points per km² on average with multi-echo) with a guaranteed relative accuracy of $EMQ_{EN} \leq 25cm$, $EMQ_H \leq 5cm$ and absolute accuracy $EMQ_{EN} \leq 50cm$, $EMQ_H \leq 10cm$ [13] respectively. In addition, the point clouds obtained are classified by a hybrid method using deterministic algorithms, probabilistic methods relying on external data and a final manual control [14]. The intensity of the return signal is a specific property of LiDAR data which is sometimes used for water surface characterization due to low reflectivity of water. Theoretically, the near-infrared wavelength used by topographic LiDARs, classically $\lambda = 1064nm$ or $\lambda = 1550nm$, allows the sensor to obtain very little return signal from a water surface [10]. In addition, intensity is however also very dependent on atmospheric transmittance and other LiDAR characteristics [15] : transmitted power; gain of the transmitter/receiving antenna; radar cross section; distance between the transmitter/receiver and the object.

Höfle [16] has shown that intensity coupled to elevation can be a good indicator for water surface identification when considering the atmospheric parameters. Deshpande [11] and Zheng [17], have rather chosen to ignore the intensity and work with the density instead because those LiDAR characteristics and

atmospheric parameters were too difficult to describe. For these reasons, the intensity of the returned signal has not been used in this study to characterize the water surface.

For scanning transmitters, the near-absence of point on water (i.e., low return signal density) is primarily due to the signal absorption by water. Some part of the signal is also refracted in the water column, while the rest is reflected, a phenomenon further accentuated by the beam's incidence angle. Therefore, to register a returned LiDAR infrared signal from the water, several conditions must be met, including the angle of incidence, water turbidity and surface conditions and the characteristics of the transmitter. This lack of data has been exploited by various authors to detect water surface. For example, Worstell [10] showed that the use of sliding windows with a radius of 5 meters on a 1 m LiDAR raster grid, containing fewer than 23 returns (i.e. 28% of the moving window), is sufficient to delineate water spaces. Deshpande [11] filled the voids by false points located much lower than the DTM and then calculated the intersection polygon between the resulting TIN DTM and a horizontal surface.

Figure 1. Aude reach (left) with points on water classified as “ground” and no “ground” point under vegetation, Hers-mort reach (right) with almost no points on water

However, if the returned signal is not systematic at the water surface due to the refraction/reflection combination, the ground surface, particularly under forest cover, is also sometimes slightly affected by the LiDAR beam due to signal absorption by dense vegetation (Fig. 1). It is thus possible to not obtain any point on the water surface neither on the ground under the surrounding vegetation. This heterogeneity makes it difficult to develop a large-scale automatic method using only density and elevation to delineate water surfaces.

III. METHOD: ITERATIVE RIVER CENTERLINE DELINEATION

The proposed method developed is based on a direct analysis of the point cloud to avoid raster interpolation and on an iterative

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Figure 2. Cloud points sectorization around the origin point (8° sectors for this representation)

The next centerline vertex identification process relies on the choice of the angular sector. This choice is based on several criteria calculated for each sector, including the point density in the sector, geometric criteria (altitude, mean distance) and semantic criteria from the point classification (presence of “Water” or “Bridge” points, presence of high vegetation) (Fig. 3). The range of values for these features has been determined so that they are minimal at the location of a theoretical water surface. These parameters are then modelled using a multi-variable linear combination where each criterion is assigned a coefficient. These coefficients were estimated by a 160-fold trained Bayesian optimization, as well as the neighborhood radius.

Figure 3. Criteria used in the research of flow direction in one sector (red dots: last centerline vertex; brown dots: ground points; blue dots: water points; green dots: vegetation points; purple dots: bridge points)

To find the sector angle that minimizes the combination of these variables, a 4-harmonic inverse Fourier transform is used to select the best candidates for stream direction (Fig. 4). The next vertex is calculated at a distance equal to one-fifth of the radius, in the direction of the best sector. Repeating the operation allows us to draw the streamline vectorially, limiting the search to a restricted radius in order to limit the mathematical constraints.

Figure 4. Modeling of the angular section criteria into a multi-variable linear combination (red) and his Fourier Transform (black)

IV. RESULTS

Can be used as a first step in the hydromorphological characterisation of rivers, the accuracy of the algorithm needs to be controlled. Indeed, if its resulting line is used as input for another automatic process, such as measuring width or slope along a river, it must, firstly, never leave the water surface polygon and, secondly, be as centered as possible within this polygon. Proven in a first study on a training set of 32 river reaches, this approach demonstrated relevant results for sites with varied characteristics (river size, sinuosity, etc.). We compared the central lines obtained with drawn reference lines. These references lines may include a bias due to manual tracing (2m to 10m edges). We segmented our lines into 100 equally-spaced points, then measured the absolute value of their distance from

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Figure 5. Error distribution in river width percentage (10% bins)

The automatically determined line remains very often close to our reference (Fig. 6), with a mean of 23.6% and a median of 8.5% of river width. Two of our cases fell victim to a drift phenomenon.

Figure 6. Choisille reach at Saint-Cyr-sur-Loire (blue line: centerline reference, red line: centerline calculated with our method, dots: LiDAR point cloud colorized according to classification)

Even if it is limited, this problem is the main limitation of this methodology and is caused by a local difficulty, mainly for the smallest rivers, in differentiating the water zone from certain riparian zones, which are often low-lying and dense cover by vegetation (i.e. therefore with few return signal points). These areas may be difficult to detect even when the references lines are determined manually.

A study of 100+ other stations is now underway to test our hyperparameters on sectors independent of the training set.

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